

BRIEF REPORT

Gaze improves working memory for verbal items

[version 1; peer review: 1 approved with reservations, 3 not approved]

Vinoprasath Shivakumar ¹, Ljerka Ostojić ¹⁻³, Edward Legg ¹⁻³¹Division of Cognitive Sciences, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, University of Rijeka, Rijeka, Primorje-Gorski Kotar, 51000, Croatia²Department of Psychology, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, University of Rijeka, Rijeka, Primorje-Gorski Kotar, 51000, Croatia³Centre For Mind and Behaviour, University of Rijeka, Rijeka, Primorje-Gorski Kotar County, 51000, Croatia

V1 First published: 20 Nov 2025, 5:355
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.21720.1>
 Latest published: 26 Feb 2026, 5:355
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.21720.2>

Abstract

Background

Previous studies have shown that stimuli that another individual looks at are better remembered than stimuli that are not looked at, suggesting that joint attention improves memory. However, these previous studies have differed in the type of memory being tested and the type of content that is to-be-remembered: while effects of joint attention on long-term memory were tested with verbalizable stimuli, effects on working memory have only been tested with visual stimuli such as colour. Thus, the aim of the current study is to extend these previous findings and investigate whether joint attention improves working memory for verbalizable stimuli.

Methods

Participants were first presented with an image of a face with eyes that gazed either to the left or to the right, after which a grid of 4 letters (2x2) was shown. On half of trials, this grid with letters was shown in the same direction that was gazed at, and in the other half of the trials, in the other direction. After a retention interval (1000 ms), participants were shown a letter in the centre of the screen and asked to judge whether they have seen this letter as part of the grid shown before.

Results

Our results revealed that participants' judgements about whether they had previously seen the letter was more accurate for letters that

Open Peer Review

Approval Status

	1	2	3	4
version 2 (revision) 26 Feb 2026				
version 1 20 Nov 2025	 view	 view	 view	 view

1. **Jari Hietanen** , Tampere University, Tampere, Finland
2. **Samantha Gregory** , University of Salford, Salford, UK
3. **Krzysztof Cipora** , Jagiellonian University in Krakow, Krakow, Poland
4. **Jeanette A. Chacón-Candia** , University of Granada, Granada, Spain

Any reports and responses or comments on the article can be found at the end of the article.

had been gazed at than letters that had not been gazed at. In contrast, participants' reaction times were not influenced by whether the letter had been gazed at.

Conclusions

Our findings suggest that joint attention can improve working memory for verbalizable stimuli such as letters.

Keywords

gaze cueing, working memory, joint attention, attention orienting

This article is included in the [Horizon 2020](#) gateway.

This article is included in the [Marie-Sklodowska-Curie Actions \(MSCA\)](#) gateway.

Corresponding author: Edward Legg (ewlegg@gmail.com)

Author roles: **Shivakumar V:** Conceptualization, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Visualization, Writing – Review & Editing; **Ostojić L:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Resources, Supervision, Visualization, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Legg E:** Conceptualization, Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Funding Acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project Administration, Resources, Software, Supervision, Visualization, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing

Competing interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Grant information: This project has received funding from the [European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme] under grant agreement No [794270] (project name [INTOM]).

The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

Copyright: © 2025 Shivakumar V *et al.* This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

How to cite this article: Shivakumar V, Ostojić L and Legg E. **Gaze improves working memory for verbal items [version 1; peer review: 1 approved with reservations, 3 not approved]** Open Research Europe 2025, 5:355 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.21720.1>

First published: 20 Nov 2025, 5:355 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.21720.1>

Introduction

The physiology of human eyes with their large white sclera and dark iris helps provide a clear signal of the direction in which an individual is looking (Kobayashi & Kohshima, 1997). A large body of research using manipulations to face and eye stimuli that reflect shifts in the iris position relative to the sclera have demonstrated that humans are remarkably sensitive to the direction of another's gaze. Already 3-month old infants shift their own attention in the direction signalled by images of eyes looking to the left or right placed on an image of a face (Hood *et al.*, 1998). For adults, such shifts in attention appear to have some degree of automatization, appearing in situations where gaze fails to predict a target's location and when participants are placed under cognitive load (Friesen & Kingstone, 1998; Visser & Roberts, 2018).

This sensitivity to the direction of another's gaze further allows two individuals to coordinate their attention toward the same external stimulus. The benefits of such 'joint attention' have been the subject of extensive discussion (Kwisthout *et al.*, 2008; Moore *et al.*, 2014; Tomasello, 1995). One strand of research on the downstream consequences of joint attention focuses on processes that have played key roles in the discussion about the evolution of joint attention – such as the impact of joint attention on word learning (Hirotoni *et al.*, 2009) and on conveying information about preferences (Bayliss *et al.*, 2006; Bayliss *et al.*, 2007). A second strand of research investigates the impact of joint attention on domain-general processes that could be affected by an individual's previous level of attention, such as working memory and long-term memory. Dodd *et al.* (2012) demonstrated the effect of gaze cues on long term memory. Participants first saw a schematic face that did not have pupils/irises. Then, the pupils/irises were shown, making the face appear to look to the left or to the right. Finally, a word was shown either to the left or to the right side of the face, such that the word appeared either on the side that the eyes were looking toward or on the opposite side. When asked to recall the words at the end of the experiment, participants remembered words better when they had appeared in the location that the central face had been looking at, suggesting that joint attention may improve long term memory of written words. Complementing these results, Gregory and Jackson (2017) found that participants showed higher accuracy of working memory for the gazed at items than the non-gazed at items. Here, participants were presented with a grid of 4, 6 or 8 coloured squares either on the side that a central face gazed toward or on the opposite side. There were thus two critical differences between these two studies. First, in Dodd *et al.* (2012), the to-be-remembered items were words, and in Gregory and Jackson (2017), they were square patches of colour – such that in the former, the memory test was based on verbalizable information, and in the latter, the memory test was based on visual information. Second, in Dodd *et al.* (2012), the test was conducted at the end of the presentation of all to-be-remembered items, and in Gregory and Jackson (2017), the test was conducted 1000 ms after the offset of the to-be-remembered items – such that in the former, long-term memory was assessed, and in the latter, working memory was assessed. Consequently, current evidence

indicates that joint attention enhances long-term memory for verbalizable information (i.e., words) and working memory for visual information (i.e., colour).

Before these results can be taken as an indication that joint attention produces improvements to different types of memory across different stimuli, it is crucial to consider that processes involved in storing verbal and non-verbal information in working memory are commonly proposed to be separate (Baddeley, 2003). While verbal information is likely being stored within the phonological loop, with information decaying rapidly unless subject to a maintenance process such as subvocal rehearsal (Camos *et al.*, 2009; although see Oberauer, 2019), non-verbal information is thought to be stored in the visuo-spatial sketchpad and is also maintained through maintenance strategies which may involve allocating attention – in the absence of the stimulus – to the spatial location of stimuli that need to be remembered (Awh *et al.*, 2006). Considering the results of both Dodd *et al.* (2012) and Gregory and Jackson (2017), this raises the question of whether joint attention only improves long-term memory for verbalizable stimuli or whether the improvement for such stimuli is also observed for working memory. Thus, the aim of the current study was test whether joint attention improves verbal working memory performance using a modified procedure of Gregory and Jackson (2017) such that the to-be-remembered items were letters.

Methods

Participants

A power analysis using the R package 'pwr' indicated that a sample size of 34 was needed to detect a medium sized effect (Cohen's $d = 0.5$) with a power of 0.8 using a paired sample t-test with the significance level set at .05. Thirty-six participants with a mean age of 38 (SD = 11.4) were recruited using Prolific.com and were compensated £2.25 for taking part in the study. The study was approved by the Ethics Committee for Research at the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, University of Rijeka [640-01/20-01/71]. All participants gave written informed consent by filling in an electronic form.

Materials

The experiment was built using jsPsych (de Leeuw *et al.*, 2023) and the jspsych-psychophysics plugin (Kuroki, 2021). The information sheets and debrief sections of the experiment were built using SurveyJS (<https://github.com/surveyjs>) and custom JavaScript.

Images of three male and three female faces from the Chicago Face Database (Ma *et al.*, 2015) were selected. Potential directional cues elicited by peripheral facial features or hair were removed by masking the entire image aside from a central oval area and turning the image to grayscale. Iris position and the lightness of the sclera was manipulated by modifying the original images using GIMP (GIMP version 2.10; <https://www.gimp.org/>) to create 3 images – where the face appeared to look straight ahead, look to the left and look to the right. The images were presented with a width of 180px.

The letters presented were consonants that appear with medium to high frequency in English (B, C, D, F, G, H, K, L, M, N, P, R, S, T; previously used by [Yeaton & Grainger, 2022](#)). Letters were always capitalized and presented in ‘Open Sans’ font with a font size of 48px and a font weight of 800.

All stimuli were presented within a HTML5 canvas element 800px by 450px. The code used to create the experiment can be found at <https://github.com/elegg/gaze-cueing-wm-verbal-experiment>. The experiment itself was deployed using JATOS ([Lange et al., 2015](#)) and hosted at <https://mindprobe.eu/>.

Procedure

At the start of each trial, a central black fixation cross was displayed for 1000 ms. This was followed by a face with direct gaze (central iris position) shown for 750 ms. An image of the same face with the position of the irises in each eye shifted either to the left or right of their previous position - to indicate a change in gaze direction - was presented for 500 ms in the absence of any other stimuli. This image continued to be displayed for a further 150 ms¹ during which a 2x2 grid of letters appeared to either the left or the right of the face. Next, a central black fixation cross was displayed for 1000 ms. The display of this fixation cross acted as the retention interval before a single black letter was presented in the centre of the screen. This letter was presented for a maximum of 3000 ms or until participants made a response. A response was made either using the up-arrow key to indicate that the letter was an item from the previously presented letter grid or the down-arrow key to indicate that the letter was absent from the

grid. Participants then received feedback for 500 ms depending on whether they had answered correctly, incorrectly or had not made a response within 3000 ms (see [Figure 1](#)).

Participants first received 12 practice trials. They then received a total of 196 trials divided into 4 blocks of 48 trials. In half of the trials, the letter grid was presented in the same direction that the eyes on the central face looked toward (*gazed at* condition; ‘valid condition’ sensu [Gregory & Jackson, 2017](#)) and in the other half, the letter grid was presented in the other direction (*gazed away* condition; ‘invalid condition’ sensu [Gregory & Jackson, 2017](#)).

Analysis

Our primary measure of interest was the discriminability index d' as an indicator how well participants could detect whether the item presented at test was one of the items they had previously been shown based on both hits (correct detections) and misses (false detections). We calculated d' as

$$Z(\text{proportion of correct detections}) - Z(\text{proportion of false detections})$$

For each participant, we calculated d' For all trial types together as well as separately for trials in the *gazed at* condition and for trials in the *gazed away* condition. Following [Gregory and Jackson \(2017\)](#), we excluded any participants whose d' score was not within 2.5 mean absolute deviations (see [Leys et al., 2013](#) for an explanation of the benefits of using mean absolute deviation to remove outliers) of the median. This led to data from one participant being excluded from the final analysis. A paired sample t-test was used to compare participants’ d' scores between the *gazed at* condition and the *gazed away* condition.

We also analysed participants’ response times. For this analysis, we first removed all trials that had incorrect responses.

¹This differs from [Gregory and Jackson \(2017\)](#) who displayed colour patches for 100ms. However, when piloting our study, participants perceived this duration to be too short such that we extended the duration to 150ms.

Figure 1. Example trial sequence. Note: An example of a trial. First a fixation cross is shown, then a face with eyes facing directly at the participant. The eyes on the face are then shown looking to the left or right and after a 500 ms stimulus onset asynchrony a grid of 4 letters appeared for 150 ms. This was followed by a 1000 ms retention interval before a probe stimulus appeared for up to 3000 ms or until the participant made a response. Participants then received feedback based on their response. Please note that due to restrictions on distributing images from the Chicago Face Database ([Ma et al., 2015](#)) a schematic image of a face has been used in place of the images used in the experiment.

For each participant, we calculated their median overall response time and their median response time for the *gazed at* condition and the *gazed away* condition. Data from participants whose median response time was not within 2.5 mean absolute deviations of the pooled median were excluded. This led to data from one participant being excluded from the final analysis. A paired sample t-test was used to compare participants' median response times between the *gazed at* condition and the *gazed away* condition.

Results

Accuracy - d'

Participants were better able to detect whether they had seen the letter before in the *gazed at* condition ($M = 2.04$, $SD = 0.79$) than in the *gazed away* condition ($M = 1.58$, $SD = 0.0.78$; $t(33) = 5.72$, $p < .001$, $d = 0.58$; [Figure 2A](#)).

Reaction times

We did not detect a statistically significant difference in the time it took participants to respond between the two conditions ($t(33) = 0.967$, $p = .34$, $d = 0.05$; *gazed at* condition: $M = 770.00$ ms, $SD = 131.00$ ms; *gazed away* condition: $M = 762.00$ ms, $SD = 133.00$ ms; [Figure 2B](#)).

Discussion

Our results showed that participants were more accurate in judging whether they had previously seen a letter when - at the time it was presented - another person appeared to be looking at it (*gazed at* condition) than when another person appeared to be looking away from it (*gazed away* condition). Further, we found no significant difference in the time it took for participants to respond to the probe trials between these two conditions, suggesting that the improvements in participants' memory of letters are not explained by participants trading their accuracy for speed in the *gazed at* condition. Thus,

in terms of the influence of gaze cues on working memory, the current results act as a conceptual replication of [Gregory and Jackson \(2017\)](#), who showed that joint attention improves working memory for non-verbalizable content such as colour, and suggest that this improvement is also possible for verbalizable content such as letter.

The effect of the gaze cue on participants' memory closely resembles the results found by [Gregory and Jackson \(2017\)](#) but our reaction time results do not. Whereas [Gregory and Jackson \(2017\)](#) found evidence that participants were faster to respond to the probe in *gazed at* trials than *gazed away* trials, we found no evidence for such an effect. The absence of this effect in the current study may be the result of the change in the type of stimulus between the two studies. Alternatively, it is possible that this effect on reaction times is only observed when working memory load is high and is thus not observable in our study - in the current study, we used only 4 to-be-remembered items whereas the original study used 4, 6 and 8 items. However, the most plausible explanation is that this may be a weak effect that was not found in the current study due to lower statistical power of the statistical test than needed to detect such an effect - an interpretation supported by the failure of other follow-up studies to reliably detect such an effect on reaction times ([Gregory & Jackson, 2019](#)). The current study was powered to detect a mid-sized effect, as expected for an effect of the gaze cue on the main measure of interest (d'). Critically, the effect of the gaze cue on participants' reaction times to a probe stimulus has limited bearing on our main question of how such gaze cues influence memory. Here, and in previous studies, the primary concern with reaction times was that participants may trade speed for accuracy such that their relatively inaccurate responding in the *gazed away* condition would be explained by them responding very fast. The absence of any such pattern of results in the current study and the inverse effect found by [Gregory and Jackson \(2017\)](#) suggest that such a trade-off is unlikely to explain the observed difference in memory accuracy. Thus, our findings extend those by [Gregory and Jackson \(2017\)](#) and suggest that joint attention can improve working memory for both verbalizable and non-verbalizable content, which are thought to be processed separately ([Baddeley, 2003](#)).

To conclude, our findings suggest that joint attention can improve working memory for verbalizable content such as letters. As such, the current results help connect two previous studies, specifically [Dodd et al. \(2012\)](#) who demonstrated that joint attention improves long-term memory for verbalizable stimuli - words - and [Gregory and Jackson \(2017\)](#) who demonstrated that joint attention improves working memory for visual stimuli - colour. Thus, our study presents an important step towards showing that joint attention can modulate different types of memory for various types of stimuli that may be represented by different subsystems.

Ethics and consent

The study was approved by the Ethics Committee for Research at the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, University of Rijeka [640-01/20-01/71].

Figure 2. Discriminability index d' and reaction times in the *gazed at* and *gazed away* conditions. Note: **A)** Box and whisker plots showing median and interquartile range of d' for the *gazed at* and *gazed away* conditions. **B)** Box and whisker plots showing median and interquartile range of participants' reaction times on correctly answered trials for the *gazed at* and *gazed away* conditions.

All participants gave informed written consent to participate by filling in an online (electronic) consent form.

Data availability statement

The raw data from certain trials of the experiment contain personal identifiable information and cannot be made publicly available due to ethical considerations. However, the following data has been made available and contains all information necessary to replicate our analysis, results and data visualisations.

Zenodo: Data From “Gaze improves working memory for verbal items”, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17491711> (Legg *et al.*, 2025a)

This project contains the following data:

- “gaze-working-memory-data.csv” which contains the trial by trial data for each participant Data are available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC-BY 4.0)

Data are available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC-BY 4.0)

Software availability statement

Software used in the experiment is available from:

- Source code available from: <https://github.com/elegg/gaze-cueing-wm-verbal-experiment>

- Archived software: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17426209>

- License: MIT License

Software used for analysis and visualisations is available from:

- Source code available from: <https://github.com/elegg/gaze-cueing-memory-verbal-analysis>

- Archived software available from: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17426275>

- License: MIT License

Extended data

Zenodo: Extended Data From “Gaze improves working memory for verbal items”,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17549330> (Legg *et al.*, 2025b)

This project contains the following data:

- Extended Data - Gaze-WM.docx (a word document containing: 1. an example consent form questionnaire, 2. an example of the instructions – text and image - presented to participants, and 3. an example of the text presented to the participant in the debrief section of the experiment).

Data are available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC-BY 4.0)

References

- Awh E, Vogel EK, Oh SH: **Interactions between attention and working memory.** *Neuroscience*. 2006; **139**(1): 201–208.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Baddeley A: **Working memory: looking back and looking forward.** *Nat Rev Neurosci*. 2003; **4**(10): 829–839.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Bayliss AP, Frischen A, Fenske MJ, *et al.*: **Affective evaluations of objects are influenced by observed gaze direction and emotional expression.** *Cognition*. 2007; **104**(3): 644–653.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Bayliss AP, Paul MA, Cannon PR, *et al.*: **Gaze cuing and affective judgments of objects: I like what you look at.** *Psychon Bull Rev*. 2006; **13**(6): 1061–1066.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Camos V, Lagner P, Barrouillet P: **Two maintenance mechanisms of verbal information in working memory.** *J Mem Lang*. 2009; **61**(3): 457–469.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- de Leeuw JR, Gilbert RA, Luchterhandt B: **jsPsych: enabling an open-source collaborative ecosystem of behavioral experiments.** *J Open Source Softw*. 2023; **8**(85): 5351.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Dodd MD, Weiss N, McDonnell GP, *et al.*: **Gaze cues influence memory...but not for long.** *Acta Psychol (Amst)*. 2012; **141**(2): 270–275.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Friesen CK, Kingstone A: **The eyes have it! Reflexive orienting is triggered by nonpredictive gaze.** *Psychon Bull Rev*. 1998; **5**(3): 490–495.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Gregory SEA, Jackson MC: **Joint attention enhances visual working memory.** *J Exp Psychol Learn Mem Cogn*. 2017; **43**(2): 237–249.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Gregory SEA, Jackson MC: **Barriers block the effect of joint attention on working memory: perspective taking matters.** *J Exp Psychol Learn Mem Cogn*. 2019; **45**(5): 795–806.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Hirotsani M, Stets M, Striano T, *et al.*: **Joint attention helps infants learn new words: event-related potential evidence.** *Neuroreport*. 2009; **20**(6): 600–5.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Hood BM, Willen JD, Driver J: **Adult's eyes Trigger shifts of visual attention in human infants.** *Psychol Sci*. 1998; **9**(2): 131–134.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Kobayashi H, Kohshima S: **Unique morphology of the human eye.** *Nature*. 1997; **387**(6635): 767–768.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Kuroki D: **A new jsPsych plugin for psychophysics, providing accurate display duration and stimulus onset asynchrony.** *Behav Res Methods*. 2021; **53**(1): 301–310.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Kwisthout J, Vogt P, Haselager P, *et al.*: **Joint attention and language evolution.** *Conn Sci*. 2008; **20**(2–3): 155–171.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Lange K, Kühn S, Filevich E: **“Just Another Tool for Online Studies” (JATOS): an easy solution for setup and management of web servers supporting online studies.** *PLoS One*. 2015; **10**(6): e0130834.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Legg E, Ostojčić L, Shivakumar V: **Data From “Gaze improves working memory**

for verbal items". [Dataset], Zenodo. 2025a.

<http://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17491711>

Legg E, Ostojic L, Shivakumar V: **Extended Data From "Gaze improves working memory for verbal items"**. [Dataset], Zenodo. 2025b.

<http://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17549330>

Leys C, Ley C, Klein O, *et al.*: **Detecting outliers: do not use standard deviation around the mean, use absolute deviation around the median.** *J Exp Soc Psychol.* 2013; **49**(4): 764–766.

[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)

Ma DS, Correll J, Wittenbrink B: **The Chicago face database: a free stimulus set of faces and norming data.** *Behav Res Methods.* 2015; **47**(4): 1122–1135.

[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)

Moore C, Dunham PJ, Dunham P: **Joint attention: its origins and role in**

development. Psychology Press, 2014.

[Publisher Full Text](#)

Oberauer K: **Is rehearsal an effective maintenance strategy for working memory?** *Trends Cogn Sci.* 2019; **23**(9): 798–809.

[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)

Tomasello M: **Joint attention as social cognition.** In: *Joint Attention.* Psychology Press, 1995.

[Reference Source](#)

Visser TAW, Roberts A: **Automaticity of social cues: the influence of limiting cognitive resources on head orientation cueing.** *Sci Rep.* 2018; **8**(1): 10288.

[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)

Yeaton JD, Grainger J: **Positional cueing, string location variability, and letter-in-string identification.** *Acta Psychol (Amst).* 2022; **223**: 103510.

[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)

Open Peer Review

Current Peer Review Status:

Version 1

Reviewer Report 08 January 2026

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.23498.r64662>

© 2026 **Chacón-Candia J.** This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Jeanette A. Chacón-Candia

University of Granada, Granada, Spain

This study aimed to investigate whether socially relevant cues modulate working memory for verbalizable information, in a similar way to what has been previously reported for colour stimuli (Gregory & Jackson, 2017). In an online experiment, participants were first presented with a central schematic face looking straight ahead, which subsequently shifted its gaze to the left or right along the horizontal axis. After 500 ms, a grid containing four letters appeared either to the left or right of the central cue. Following a retention interval indicated by a fixation cross, a single probe letter was presented. Participants were required to indicate whether the probe letter had been part of the previously presented letter grid.

Using this paradigm, the authors examined whether working memory was enhanced when the letter grid appeared at the location cued by gaze, or whether gaze-target congruency did not influence participants' ability to remember the letters.

The authors found that participants were more accurate in remembering the letters when the grid appeared at the gazed-at location than when it appeared on the opposite side. Based on these results, they conclude that joint attention can enhance working memory for verbalizable stimuli, such as letters.

Before providing my comments on the manuscript, I would like to note that I consider the investigation of social attention and its connection with other cognitive functions, such as working memory, to be an interesting and valuable area of research. It is encouraging to see how other authors are engaging in this line of work and contributing to the expansion of the literature on these interesting topic.

General Comments and Suggestions

- A relevant point that I believe could strengthen the manuscript concerns the relationship between the present findings and previous work by Gregory and Jackson (2017). The authors repeatedly state that their paradigm is highly comparable to that study and explicitly build on its

theoretical framework. However, an important methodological difference should be acknowledged.

In Gregory and Jackson (2017), a direct comparison was made between socially relevant cues (eye-gaze) and non-social cues (arrows and low-level motion cues). Their central conclusion (that eye-gaze selectively modulates working memory) was explicitly based on this contrast, leading the authors to argue that the effect was driven by the social relevance of gaze. In the present study, by contrast, only socially relevant cues (eye-gaze) are included. As a result, the paradigm does not allow for a direct test of whether the observed effects are specific to social cues or could also be elicited by non-social directional cues.

Despite this limitation, the authors draw conclusions that closely mirror those of Gregory and Jackson (2017), attributing the observed working memory benefits for verbalizable stimuli to social mechanisms such as joint attention. Without including a non-social control condition, however, these claims appear less strongly supported. Explicitly discussing this methodological difference, and tempering the theoretical conclusions, accordingly, would improve the clarity and strength of the manuscript.

Building on this point, it may be relevant for the authors to consider recent meta-analytic evidence questioning the social specificity of the classic gaze-cueing paradigm. Specifically, Chacón-Candia et al. (2023) showed that, at a quantitative level, the classic gaze-cueing task does not produce effects that reliably differ from those elicited by non-social cues such as arrows. This evidence suggests that the attentional orienting effects observed in standard gaze-cueing paradigms may reflect domain-general mechanisms rather than uniquely social processes.

In light of this, taking into account this literature, and maybe extending the current design to include an appropriate non-social control cue (e.g., arrows), or at least discussing this limitation explicitly, would substantially strengthen the manuscript. In particular, a qualitative comparison between social and non-social cues within the working memory task would allow the authors to more convincingly support claims regarding the role of joint attention or social relevance in modulating working memory performance.

- Following the previous point, it may be worth expanding the theoretical background to include additional recent studies examining the relationship between social attentional orienting and working memory. Although these studies do not focus exclusively on verbal working memory or employ identical experimental paradigms, they are nevertheless highly relevant to the aims of the present work, as they address how socially relevant cues influence attention and working memory processes.

For example, studies such as Foglino & Wykowska (2025), Nie et al. (2018), and Zhang et al. (2023) provide important evidence showing how social attention can modulate working memory performance under different task conditions. I consider that including this literature would help better situate the present findings within the broader field and strengthen the theoretical framework of the study.

Minor comments / clarifications

- Out of curiosity, it would be helpful to report the age range of the participants. Given that the mean age is 38 years, this seems relatively high, maybe providing the full range would help to

better characterize the sample.

- The manuscript mentions that two participants were excluded based on the criterion of 2.5 mean absolute deviations. However, it is not entirely clear how many participants were included in the final sample after exclusions. We suggest clarifying this information explicitly in the Participants section.

- It is not reported in the manuscript whether the hypotheses were pre-registered prior to data collection. If the study was not pre-registered, we would simply encourage the authors to consider this practice in future work, as it can enhance transparency and reproducibility.

References

1. Chacón-Candia J, Román-Caballero R, Aranda-Martín B, Casagrande M, et al.: Are there quantitative differences between eye-gaze and arrow cues? A meta-analytic answer to the debate and a call for qualitative differences. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*. 2023; **144**. [Publisher Full Text](#)
2. Foglino C, Wykowska A: Joint attention supports working memory when gaze cues are reliable and task-relevant. *Attention, Perception, & Psychophysics*. 2026; **88** (1). [Publisher Full Text](#)
3. Nie Q, Ding X, Chen J, Conci M: Social attention directs working memory maintenance. *Cognition*. 2018; **171**: 85-94 [Publisher Full Text](#)
4. Zhang Y, Ye S, Chen W, Ding X: When “looking at nothing” imparts something: Retrospective gaze cues flexibly direct prioritization in visual working memory. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Human Perception and Performance*. 2023; **49** (11): 1407-1419 [Publisher Full Text](#)

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it engage with the current literature?

Yes

Is the study design appropriate and is the work technically sound?

Partly

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

Are all the source data and materials underlying the results available?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

No

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Social Attention, Social Cognition

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of

expertise to state that I do not consider it to be of an acceptable scientific standard, for reasons outlined above.

Author Response 19 Jan 2026

Edward Legg

Dear Dr. Chacón Candia,

Many thanks for your thorough and helpful comments on the original version of our manuscript. We have changed the manuscript according to your comments, all of which also align with the comments by the other reviewers. This refers to two main aspects, namely the inclusion of a second experiment that tests the effects of both social cues (gaze cue) and non-social cues (arrow cue) on recall of verbal items in working memory, and the expansion of the theoretical discussions in this research field.

Below we provide point-by-point responses to your comments on the original version of our manuscript – for this we have pasted your comments in italics and provide our replies in plain font.

This study aimed to investigate whether socially relevant cues modulate working memory for verbalizable information, in a similar way to what has been previously reported for colour stimuli (Gregory & Jackson, 2017). In an online experiment, participants were first presented with a central schematic face looking straight ahead, which subsequently shifted its gaze to the left or right along the horizontal axis. After 500 ms, a grid containing four letters appeared either to the left or right of the central cue. Following a retention interval indicated by a fixation cross, a single probe letter was presented. Participants were required to indicate whether the probe letter had been part of the previously presented letter grid. Using this paradigm, the authors examined whether working memory was enhanced when the letter grid appeared at the location cued by gaze, or whether gaze-target congruency did not influence participants' ability to remember the letters. The authors found that participants were more accurate in remembering the letters when the grid appeared at the gazed-at location than when it appeared on the opposite side. Based on these results, they conclude that joint attention can enhance working memory for verbalizable stimuli, such as letters. Before providing my comments on the manuscript, I would like to note that I consider the investigation of social attention and its connection with other cognitive functions, such as working memory, to be an interesting and valuable area of research. It is encouraging to see how other authors are engaging in this line of work and contributing to the expansion of the literature on these interesting topic. General Comments and Suggestions - A relevant point that I believe could strengthen the manuscript concerns the relationship between the present findings and previous work by Gregory and Jackson (2017). The authors repeatedly state that their paradigm is highly comparable to that study and explicitly build on its theoretical framework. However, an important methodological difference should be acknowledged. In Gregory and Jackson (2017), a direct comparison was made between socially relevant cues (eye-gaze) and non-social cues (arrows and low-level motion cues). Their central conclusion (that eye-gaze selectively modulates working memory) was explicitly based on this contrast, leading the authors to argue that the effect was driven by the social relevance of gaze. In the present study, by contrast, only socially relevant cues (eye-gaze) are included. As a result, the paradigm does not allow for a direct test of whether the observed effects are specific to social cues or could also be elicited by non-social directional cues. Despite this limitation, the authors draw conclusions that closely mirror those of Gregory and Jackson (2017), attributing the

observed working memory benefits for verbalizable stimuli to social mechanisms such as joint attention. Without including a non-social control condition, however, these claims appear less strongly supported. Explicitly discussing this methodological difference, and tempering the theoretical conclusions, accordingly, would improve the clarity and strength of the manuscript.

Response: Thank you for these comments. We have opted to conduct a second experiment, in which we directly compared gaze cues and arrow cues. The results of this second experiment showed cueing effects on recall by both gaze cues (thus replicating our original findings) and arrow cues. We discuss these findings in the revised Discussion section, which we have now extended to also discuss methodological differences to the Gregory and Jackson (2017) but also other previous studies, and what conclusions can be drawn based on these comparisons across studies.

Building on this point, it may be relevant for the authors to consider recent meta-analytic evidence questioning the social specificity of the classic gaze-cueing paradigm. Specifically, Chacón-Candia et al. (2023) showed that, at a quantitative level, the classic gaze-cueing task does not produce effects that reliably differ from those elicited by non-social cues such as arrows. This evidence suggests that the attentional orienting effects observed in standard gaze-cueing paradigms may reflect domain-general mechanisms rather than uniquely social processes.

Response: Thank you for making us aware of this meta-analysis. It is particularly relevant given that our Experiment 2 finds a similar effect in both the gaze and arrow group. We have now included this meta-analysis when we relate the findings from standard detection tasks to those investigating cueing on recall in memory tasks.

In light of this, taking into account this literature, and maybe extending the current design to include an appropriate non-social control cue (e.g., arrows), or at least discussing this limitation explicitly, would substantially strengthen the manuscript. In particular, a qualitative comparison between social and non-social cues within the working memory task would allow the authors to more convincingly support claims regarding the role of joint attention or social relevance in modulating working memory performance.

Response: Thank you for the suggestions. We felt it would be most appropriate to run a second experiment with a non-social control. The results of this second experiment showed cueing effects on recall by both gaze cues (thus replicating our original findings) and arrow cues, which are discussed further in the revised Discussion section, which has now also been expanded.

- Following the previous point, it may be worth expanding the theoretical background to include additional recent studies examining the relationship between social attentional orienting and working memory. Although these studies do not focus exclusively on verbal working memory or employ identical experimental paradigms, they are nevertheless highly relevant to the aims of the present work, as they address how socially relevant cues influence attention and working memory processes. For example, studies such as Foglino & Wykowska (2025), Nie et al. (2018), and Zhang et al. (2023) provide important evidence showing how social attention can modulate working memory performance under different task conditions. I consider that including this literature would help better situate the present findings within the broader field and strengthen the theoretical framework of the study.

Response: Thank you for highlighting these studies. Originally, we were constrained by a word limit on brief reports, however we have now expanded both our Introduction and Discussion, and we have included these three studies too.

Minor comments / clarifications

- *Out of curiosity, it would be helpful to report the age range of the participants. Given that the mean age is 38 years, this seems relatively high, maybe providing the full range would help to better characterize the sample.*

Response: We have now provided information about the age range along with the mean and standard deviation that we reported previously.

- *The manuscript mentions that two participants were excluded based on the criterion of 2.5 mean absolute deviations. However, it is not entirely clear how many participants were included in the final sample after exclusions. We suggest clarifying this information explicitly in the Participants section.*

Response: We have now added information about final sample sizes used in the analysis for both our experiments.

- *It is not reported in the manuscript whether the hypotheses were pre-registered prior to data collection. If the study was not pre-registered, we would simply encourage the authors to consider this practice in future work, as it can enhance transparency and reproducibility.*

Response: Thank you for the suggestion, and we agree on the usefulness of pre-registrations for transparency of research. We had not pre-registered the original study, which was the outcome of a student project (not that students projects cannot or should not be pre-registered, indeed we teach students about preregistrations), which is why we also did not think of pre-registering the second experiment simply because we did not think about it at the time. At the time we ran the second experiment we had not yet received your review (it was clear from the previous reviews that running an experiment with a non-social control was the best course of action). We will take this as a good reminder to incorporate pre-registrations into our workflow.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 29 December 2025

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.23498.r64660>

© 2025 Cipora K. This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Krzysztof Cipora

Copernicus Center for Interdisciplinary Studies, Jagiellonian University in Krakow, Krakow, Poland

In the paper the authors show how cuing with a directed gaze affects working memory measured

with accuracy of probe recognition depending on whether the stimuli set was presented on the cued or non-cued side. The authors report better accuracy for cued than non-cued stimuli, while there is no difference in terms of reaction times.

The paper reads very well and clearly communicates what the authors have done (also followed by shared materials), what results they obtained and how they interpret the results. Thus I can see a merit in its publication at some point. At the same time, I would like to raise rather critical points when it comes to interpretation of the results both in terms of joint attention and in terms of crucial role of working memory.

Joint attention aspect: In studies demonstrating cuing paradigm (more or less along the lines of M. Posner model of attention), the basic stimulus used to guide participants' attention (in a so-called endogenous paradigm) have been arrows. They facilitate detection of a stimulus presented laterally on the cued side etc. See e.g., a rather classic paper by Raz & Buhle 2006 (<https://doi.org/10.1038/nrn1903>). See also a recent review on the cuing with eye gaze: <https://doi.org/10.1037/bul0000353>

To be able to show that the effect is due to social cues in particular (and joint attention) one would need to either (a) dissociate this effect from effect caused by non-social stimuli (e.g., arrows), (b) provide a compelling theoretical argument that the effect of cuing is related to joint attention event without the social aspect of the cue. The latter to my understanding is not so obvious - even without social aspect there is an adaptive advantage of attention functioning this way, and Posner's model provides quite a lot of such arguments.

Working memory aspect: if we assume that cuing mechanism takes place, it implies that spatial attention is directed towards a specific location and tuned to perceive the stimuli appearing in that location. In case of incongruent trial, the attention is directed elsewhere, it needs to be re-allocated to the place where the stimulus is actually presented. Only following that process the information about the stimulus is gathered. Given the stimulus presentation time is rather limited (150ms), the re-orienting of attention might be taking some extra time and resources, leaving less time to properly encode the stimulus. In short: the effects do not necessarily originate from the functioning of working memory.

References

1. Raz A, Buhle J: Typologies of attentional networks. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*. 2006; **7** (5): 367-379 [Publisher Full Text](#)
2. McKay K, Grainger S, Coundouris S, Skorich D, et al.: Visual attentional orienting by eye gaze: A meta-analytic review of the gaze-cueing effect. *Psychological Bulletin*. 2021; **147** (12): 1269-1289 [Publisher Full Text](#)

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it engage with the current literature?

Partly

Is the study design appropriate and is the work technically sound?

No

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

Are all the source data and materials underlying the results available?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Partly

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Cognitive psychology, numerical cognition with some expertise in attention and working memory.

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to state that I do not consider it to be of an acceptable scientific standard, for reasons outlined above.

Author Response 19 Jan 2026

Edward Legg

Dear Prof. Cipora,

Thank you for the thoughtful and detailed comments to the original version to our manuscript. In line with your and the other reviewers' comments, we opted to conduct a second experiment in which we tested two new groups of participants: one with gaze cues as the orienting cue, and one with arrow cues as the orienting cue. The results show that recall of verbal items was modulated by gaze cues (thus replicating the findings of our original experiment – now experiment 1) but also by arrow cues.

In line with your suggestions to expand the discussion of conceptual questions and possible mechanisms, we have now expanded both the introduction and discussion sections. In the latter, we interpret the observed findings in line with orienting cues having shifted participants' spatial attention.

Below we provide point-by-point responses to your comments on the original version of our manuscript – for this we have pasted your comments in italics and provide our replies in plain font.

In the paper the authors show how cuing with a directed gaze affects working memory measured with accuracy of probe recognition depending on whether the stimuli set was presented on the cued or non-cued side. The authors report better accuracy for cued than non-cued stimuli, while there is no difference in terms of reaction times. The paper reads very well and clearly communicates what the authors have done (also followed by shared materials), what results they obtained and how they interpret the results. Thus I can see a merit in its publication at some point. At the same time, I would like to raise rather critical points when it comes to interpretation of the results both in terms of joint attention and in terms of crucial role of working memory. Joint attention aspect: In studies demonstrating cuing paradigm (more or less along the lines of

M. Posner model of attention), the basic stimulus used to guide participants' attention (in a so-called endogenous paradigm) have been arrows. They facilitate detection of a stimulus presented laterally on the cued side etc. See e.g., a rather classic paper by Raz & Buhle 2006 (<https://doi.org/10.1038/nrn1903>). See also a recent review on the cuing with eye gaze: <https://doi.org/10.1037/bul0000353> To be able to show that the effect is due to social cues in particular (and joint attention) one would need to either (a) dissociate this effect from effect caused by non-social stimuli (e.g., arrows), (b) provide a compelling theoretical argument that the effect of cuing in related to joint attention event without the social aspect of the cue. The latter to my understanding is not so obvious - even without social aspect there is an adaptive advantage of attention functioning this way, and Posner's model provides quite a lot of such arguments.

Response: Thank you for these comments. We agree that a non-social control is a critical step toward showing that a cueing effect is specific to social stimuli. We have now conducted a second experiment which we report in the revised version of the manuscript. The results of this second experiment replicated the effect of gaze cues on recall for verbal items but also showed an equivalent effect of arrow cues on recall.

Working memory aspect: if we assume that cuing mechanism takes place, it implies that spatial attention is directed towards a specific location and tuned to perceive the stimuli appearing in that location. In case of incongruent trial, the attention is directed elsewhere, it needs to be re-allocated to the place where the stimulus is actually presented. Only following that process the information about the stimulus is gathered. Given the stimulus presentation time is rather limited (150ms), the re-orienting of attention might be taking some extra time and resources, leaving less time to properly encode the stimulus. In short: the effects do not necessarily originate from the functioning of working memory.

Response: Thank you for raising this point. We agree and this is particularly pertinent in light of our second experiment because in the absence of a difference between the gaze and arrow groups, it is possible that the cueing effects are explained by a shift in spatial attention at encoding. We discuss this in detail in the Discussion section of the revised manuscript.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 27 December 2025

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.23498.r64661>

© 2025 Gregory S. This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Samantha Gregory

University of Salford, Salford, England, UK

The manuscript presents a single study investigating whether gaze cues affect working memory for verbalizable items. The findings show an effect of gaze on memory for these items. The study is justified and the findings as they are presented are clear and well presented.

However, I have a few concerns.

While the basis of the study being Dodd et al 2012, and Gregory and Jackson 2017 was clear, there was a limited literature base drawn upon, and while this is a brief report some consideration of more recent findings in the area would be appropriate.

It is also notable that there was no control comparison conducted, in previous gaze cuing work mentioned, such as Gregory and Jackson, Dodd et al, and Bayliss et al 2006, an arrow cue was used as a non-social control stimuli. This comparison is required to be able to claim a social cuing effect. I believe this gap should at least be considered in the manuscript, even if not directly tested.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it engage with the current literature?

Partly

Is the study design appropriate and is the work technically sound?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

Are all the source data and materials underlying the results available?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Partly

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Social gaze cuing, attention, working memory

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 19 Jan 2026

Edward Legg

Dear Dr. Gregory,

Thank you for your comments to the original version to our manuscript, which helped us in the revision process. Based on your comments – all of which also align with the other reviewers' comments – we have changed two main things in the revised manuscript: first, we have expanded the overview of the research field and the discussions within both in the Introduction and Discussion sections, and second, we have conducted and now report a second experiment, in which we tested the effect on recall of both gaze cues and arrow

cues. This experiment revealed that both gaze and arrow cues improved participants' performance in the working memory task, such that in the discussion we now include a possible and most parsimonious interpretation based on shifts in spatial attention. Below we provide point-by-point responses to your comments on the original version of our manuscript – for this we have pasted your comments in italics and provide our replies in plain font.

The manuscript presents a single study investigating whether gaze cues affect working memory for verbalizable items. The findings show an effect of gaze on memory for these items. The study is justified and the findings as they are presented are clear and well presented. However, I have a few concerns. While the basis of the study being Dodd et al 2012, and Gregory and Jackson 2017 was clear, there was a limited literature base drawn upon, and while this is a brief report some consideration of more recent findings in the area would be appropriate.

We thank you for the suggestion to expand the Introduction. We were initially constrained by the word limit of the brief report, but we have now expanded the Introduction section of the revised manuscript, such that a more thorough overview of the literature and the debates within it are provided to the reader.

It is also notable that there was no control comparison conducted, in previous gaze cuing work mentioned, such as Gregory and Jackson, Dodd et al, and Bayliss et al 2006, an arrow cue was used as a non-social control stimuli. This comparison is required to be able to claim a social cuing effect. I believe this gap should at least be considered in the manuscript, even if not directly tested.

We have now conducted a second experiment which we report in the revised version of the manuscript, in which we replicated the effect of gaze cues on recall for verbal items but also found an equivalent effect of arrow cues on recall. In relating these results to previous literature, we have now also expanded the Discussion section.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 25 November 2025

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.23498.r64659>

© 2025 Hietanen J. This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Jari Hietanen

Tampere University, Tampere, Finland

The manuscript describes a single study investigating the effect of gaze cuing on working memory, specifically for retention of verbal information (a matrix of 4 letters). The results showed that the participants were more accurate in judging whether a target letter (presented 1000 ms after the presentation of the matrix) had been among letters in the matrix when the matrix

appeared at the gaze-at location than when it appeared at the opposite location. The authors interpreted the results to show that “joint attention can improve working memory for verbalizable content such as letters”.

As a basis for their study, the authors refer to two previous studies which investigated the effects of gaze cuing on long-term retention of verbal stimuli (Dodd et al., 2012) and the effects of gaze cuing on short-term (working memory) retention of non-verbal visual information (colors) (Gregory & Jackson, 2017). The authors motivate their study by arguing that they aim to investigate whether gaze cuing (or joint attention as they call it) improves also verbal working memory performance.

The aim of the study is justified. However, if the authors aim to show that joint attention improves verbal working memory, they should be able to show that the reported findings are not just reflecting general attentional effects. In studies by both Dodd et al. (2012) and by Gregory & Jackson (2017) this was achieved by showing that attention cuing by symbolic cues (arrows) did not result in better memory performance for cued vs. uncued stimuli. I am somewhat surprised that the authors of the present manuscript do not describe this aspect of those two previous studies at all, nor they discuss the potential issue related to attentional vs. memory effects behind their findings in their discussion either. By the way, there is also a more recent study by Ishikawa and Yoshioka (2025) in which they also used the same approach (i.e. comparing gaze cuing vs arrow cuing).

Thus, I am afraid but the present study cannot provide convincing evidence that joint attention improves verbal working memory performance.

Otherwise, the experiment appeared to be carefully conducted and the results were appropriately analyzed.

As a minor issue, in Methods, the authors could mention that, on each trial, the letters in the matrix were randomly selected among the used consonants. I take that this was the case. Also, I suppose that the target letter was one of those presented in the matrix on half of the trials, and that this manipulation was orthogonal to that of the cuing (i.e. cued vs uncued).

Reference

Ishikawa, M., Yoshioka, A. Gaze cues facilitate incidental learning in children aged 7–10 years, but arrow cues do not. *Psychon Bull Rev* **32**, 1712–1721 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13423-025-02657-x>

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it engage with the current literature?

Partly

Is the study design appropriate and is the work technically sound?

No

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Partly

Are all the source data and materials underlying the results available?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

No

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Cognitive psychology/attention orienting by gaze cuing

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to state that I do not consider it to be of an acceptable scientific standard, for reasons outlined above.

Author Response 19 Jan 2026

Edward Legg

Dear Prof. Hietanen, Thank you for the thoughtful comments to the original version to our manuscript. In light of your and the other reviewers' comments, we have opted to conduct a second experiment. Our intention had been to provide data and a short report regarding the first step in testing whether orienting cues affect recall in a working memory task for verbal content, without necessarily going further into what may underlie this effect. However, in light of your and the other reviewers' comments, all of which we agree with, we have opted to conduct a second experiment. In this second experiment, we tested two new groups of participants, one for whom the orienting cue was a gaze cue (direct replication of Experiment 1., i.e., the study reported in the original version of our manuscript) and one for whom the orienting cue was an arrow cue. Here, we found that both gaze and arrow cues improved participants' performance in the working memory task. Consequently, we have expanded our discussion to include an interpretation based on shifts in spatial attention (which provides the most likely and parsimonious explanation for our pattern of results), but where we also briefly discuss avenues for future research that are opened up by these results. Below we provide point-by-point responses to your comments on the original version of our manuscript – for this we have pasted your comments in italics and provide our replies in plain font.

The manuscript describes a single study investigating the effect of gaze cuing on working memory, specifically for retention of verbal information (a matrix of 4 letters). The results showed that the participants were more accurate in judging whether a target letter (presented 1000 ms after the presentation of the matrix) had been among letters in the matrix when the matrix appeared at the gaze-at location than when it appeared at the opposite location. The authors interpreted the results to show that "joint attention can improve working memory for verbalizable content such as letters". As a basis for their study, the authors refer to two previous studies which investigated the effects of gaze cuing on long-term retention of verbal stimuli (Dodd et al., 2012) and the effects of gaze cuing on short-term (working memory) retention of non-verbal visual information (colors) (Gregory & Jackson, 2017). The authors motivate their study by arguing that

they aim to investigate whether gaze cuing (or joint attention as they call it) improves also verbal working memory performance. The aim of the study is justified. However, if the authors aim to show that joint attention improves verbal working memory, they should be able to show that the reported findings are not just reflecting general attentional effects. In studies by both Dodd et al. (2012) and by Gregory & Jackson (2017) this was achieved by showing that attention cuing by symbolic cues (arrows) did not result in better memory performance for cued vs. uncued stimuli. I am somewhat surprised that the authors of the present manuscript do not describe this aspect of those two previous studies at all, nor they discuss the potential issue related to attentional vs. memory effects behind their findings in their discussion either. By the way, there is also a more recent study by Ishikawa and Yoshioka (2025) in which they also used the same approach (i.e. comparing gaze cuing vs arrow cuing).

Thank you for the comment – we have now conducted a second experiment which we report in the revised version of the manuscript, and which is described in more detail also in our general reply to the reviewers' comments. The results of this second experiment – whereby we replicate the effect of gaze cues on recall for verbal items but also found an equivalent effect of arrow cues on recall – are now also discussed in terms of the most likely explanation through general attentional effects. We are also grateful for the information about the recent Ishikawa and Yoshioka (2025) study, which we had missed, and have now included it in the Introduction of the revised manuscript.

Thus, I am afraid but the present study cannot provide convincing evidence that joint attention improves verbal working memory performance. Otherwise, the experiment appeared to be carefully conducted and the results were appropriately analyzed. As a minor issue, in Methods, the authors could mention that, on each trial, the letters in the matrix were randomly selected among the used consonants. I take that this was the case. Also, I suppose that the target letter was one of those presented in the matrix on half of the trials, and that this manipulation was orthogonal to that of the cuing (i.e. cued vs uncued).

Thank you for alerting us that we missed to provide this information in the Methods of the original manuscript - we have now added information about the randomisation. The reviewer is correct that the target letter had been present in the array of consonants on half of trials and we have now described this in the Methods section of the revised manuscript.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.